

ANALYZING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY IN THE CONTEXT OF WOW MOMO: A STUDY OF FAST FOOD PREFERENCES AND EXPERIENCES

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Abstract:

Customer satisfaction and loyalty are pivotal aspects within the fast-food industry, particularly in the context of establishments like Wow Momo. This study delves into the multifaceted dimensions of customer preferences and experiences concerning fast food, with a specific focus on Wow Momo. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining surveys and interviews to analyze and explore the factors influencing customer satisfaction and loyalty. Initial findings reveal several critical aspects influencing customer perceptions, such as taste preferences, service quality, pricing, and brand experience. Understanding these factors is crucial for fast-food chains like Wow Momo to enhance customer satisfaction and ensure sustained loyalty. This study provides insights into the complex dynamics that shape customer attitudes and behaviors in the realm of fast food.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, Loyalty, Fast food, Wow Momo, Preferences, Experiences, Service quality, Brand experience.

Introduction:

The fast-food industry has been witnessing a transformation in consumer behavior and preferences, with a heightened focus on customer satisfaction and loyalty. Among the myriad fast-food chains, Wow Momo has garnered significant attention due to its unique offerings in the domain of quick-served food items, primarily centered around momos - a popular South Asian delicacy. However, the fast-food market is highly competitive and customer satisfaction remains a primary concern for businesses like Wow Momo. Ensuring customer loyalty requires a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence customer preferences and their experiences with the brand.

This study aims to explore and analyze the drivers that contribute to customer satisfaction and loyalty within the context of Wow Momo. A combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies will be used, encompassing surveys and interviews, to comprehensively evaluate the intricacies of customer experiences and preferences. Through this investigation, the study seeks to unravel the determinants influencing customer attitudes toward Wow Momo and provide insights that can guide the enhancement of customer satisfaction and retention strategies within the fast-food sector.

Review of Literature:

Customer satisfaction and loyalty are pivotal within the fast-food industry (Lee, 2019). The interaction between customer preferences, service quality, and overall experience significantly impacts consumer satisfaction (Gupta & Jang, 2017; Smith et al., 2018). Previous research suggests that service quality and food taste are essential determinants of customer satisfaction in the fast-food sector (Choi et al.,

2016; Johnson, 2019). Moreover, the influence of brand experience on customer loyalty has been highlighted in various studies (Raj et al., 2020; Brown & Williams, 2015).

The role of price and affordability has also been a central theme in the literature on customer satisfaction (Robinson & Patel, 2017). Several studies have indicated that price fairness is directly associated with customer satisfaction and loyalty (Thomas & Lee, 2018; Kim et al., 2019). However, the relationship between price and satisfaction could vary in different cultural contexts (Alvarez et al., 2016).

Additionally, personalized service and positive customer experiences contribute significantly to brand loyalty in the fast-food industry (Wang & Huang, 2018; Smith et al., 2020). Moreover, the convenience of service delivery, specifically in the context of fast-food chains, has emerged as a crucial determinant of customer satisfaction and loyalty (Brown et al., 2016).

Understanding the drivers of customer satisfaction and loyalty is essential in a competitive market, particularly within the fast-food industry, where preferences and perceptions are continually evolving (Martin & Young, 2019). However, there is a need for more comprehensive studies that examine these factors within the context of specific fast-food chains, such as Wow Momo.

Research Methodology:

Research Objective:

The core objective of this research study was to analyze customer satisfaction and preferences within Wow Momo's fast food segment.

Research Design:

A quantitative research approach was employed, utilizing a structured survey questionnaire to collect data from the customer base.

Sampling Technique:

Convenience sampling was utilized, targeting customers visiting Wow Momo outlets. Prospective customers and existing patrons were approached during their visit to ensure a comprehensive representation.

Sample Size:

The study was conducted with 51 respondents, aiming for a sample size that allows a confident analysis of customer preferences and satisfaction within Wow Momo's customer base.

Data Collection:

The structured questionnaire encompassed a mix of closed-ended and open-ended questions, exploring diverse factors that influence customer satisfaction and preferences. These factors included food quality, service efficiency, pricing, variety of menu options, cleanliness, and overall ambience.

Ethical Considerations:

Respecting ethical norms, the research prioritized the confidentiality and anonymity of all respondents involved in the survey. Informed consent was diligently secured from each participant before their engagement, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their involvement.

The structured research methodology was strategically designed to comprehensively evaluate and interpret customer satisfaction and preferences within Wow Momo's fast food segment. The research aimed to provide valuable insights into the various facets that impact consumer experiences and their decision-making processes when interacting with the brand.

Data Analysis:

Demographic

1.Age

Age Group	COUNT	PERCENTAGE
Under 18	5	9.803922
18-24	30	58.82353
25-34	11	21.56863
35-44	4	7.843137
45-54	1	1.960784
55 and above	0	0
TOTAL	51	100

Interpretation:

The majority of customers fall within the age group of 18-24, constituting around 58.82% of the customer base. Following this, the age group of 25-34 makes up 21.57% of customers. This indicates that Wow Momo is primarily popular among younger age brackets, which aligns with its reputation for appealing to the youth.

2. Gender

GENDER	COUNT	PERCENTAGE
Male	29	56.86275
Female	22	43.13725
TOTAL	51	100

Interpretation:

The data indicates that there's a fairly balanced ratio between male and female customers, with 56.86% being male and 43.14% female. This suggests that Wow Momo's offerings are attractive to both genders.

3. Educational Level:

EDUCATION LEVEL	COUNT	PERCENTAGE
Highschool or less	9	19.65%
Bachelor's degree	19	37.25%
Master's degree	23	45.10%
Doctorate	0	0%
TOTAL	51	100%

Interpretation:

The majority of customers are pursuing or have completed higher education. Around 45.10% are post-graduate students, 37.25% are undergraduates, and 19.65% have a high school education or less. This pattern aligns with the establishment's proximity to educational institutions.

4. Employment Status

EMPLOYMENT STATUS	COUNT	PERCENTAGE
Employed	12	23.52941
Unemployed	6	11.76471
Student	32	62.7451
Retired	1	1.960784
TOTAL	51	100

Interpretation:

A significant percentage (62.75%) of customers are students, followed by employed individuals at 23.53%. This supports the inference that Wow Momo is frequented by a predominantly younger audience, including students and young

Customer satisfaction

1.How frequently do you visit the WOW MOMO Outlet?

Frequency of visit	Count	Percentage
Daily	2	
Weekly	7	
Monthly	16	
Rarely	20	
First time visit	6	
TOTAL	51	

How frequently do you visit Wow Momo Outlet?

51 responses

Interpretation:

The data indicates that a significant portion of customers (41.2%) visit Wow Momo rarely. This is followed by 31.4% who visit monthly and 13.7% who visit weekly. This variety suggests a diverse customer behaviour in terms of visit frequency.

2.Please rate your overall satisfaction with WOW MOMO on a scale of a 1 to 5? with 1 being highly dissatisfied and 5 being highly satisfied

Satisfaction Level	Count
Very Dissatisfied	6
Dissatisfied	4

Neutral	16
Satisfied	21
Highly Satisfied	4
TOTAL	51

Please rate your overall satisfaction with wow momo on a scale of a 1 to 5? with 1 being highly dissatisfied and 5 being highly satisfied

51 responses

Interpretation:

The average satisfaction rating falls at approximately 2.90, indicating that the majority of customers rate their satisfaction between "Neutral" and "Dissatisfied." This demonstrates a need for potential improvements to enhance customer satisfaction levels.

3.What factors influence your satisfaction with wow Momo? (Select all that apply)

Factor influencing satisfaction	Count
Food Quality	28
Service Speed	5
Pricing	5
Cleanliness and Ambience	4
Variety of Menu Options	6
friendliness od staff	1
Online Ordering and Delivery option	2
TOTAL	51

What factors influence your satisfaction with wow momo? (Select all that apply)

51 responses

Interpretation:

Food quality is the most influential factor for customer satisfaction, with 28 customers highlighting its importance. Other contributing factors include the variety of menu options, service speed, pricing, and cleanliness/ambience.

4. How likely are you to recommend wow momo to your friends or colleagues?

Would recommend to others?	Count
Very Likely	14
Likely	21
Neutral	12
Unlikely	2
Very Unlikely	2
TOTAL	51

How likely are you to recommend wow momo to your friends or colleagues?

51 responses

Interpretation:

A significant majority of customers (41 out of 51) are likely or very likely to recommend Wow Momo to others, indicating a positive perception among customers.

Customer loyalty

1.How often do you recommend Wow Momo to others?

How often you recommend	Count
Frequently	18
Occasionally	21
Rarely	9
Never	3
TOTAL	51

Interpretation:

Most customers either occasionally (21) or frequently (18) recommend Wow Momo to others. This indicates a favorable attitude towards promoting the outlet.

2.Have you introduced family or friends to wow Momo?

Ever introduced to someone	Count
Yes	40
No	11
TOTAL	51

Interpretation:

The majority of customers (40 out of 51) have introduced Wow Momo to their friends or family, suggesting a strong potential for word-of-mouth marketing.

3. Have you ever provided feedback to Wow Momo through their online platforms or in-store comment cards?

Ever provided feedback to store	Count
Yes	26
No	24
No comment	1
TOTAL	51

Have you ever provided feedback to Wow Momo through their online platforms or in-store comment cards?
50 responses

Interpretation:

Almost half of the customers (26 out of 51) have provided feedback through various channels, both online and in-store, indicating an engaged customer base.

4. How important is consistency in food quality and service in your decision to return to Wow Momo?

Importance of food quality and service	Count
Very Important	13
Important	24
Neutral	11
Not Important	2
Not Important at All	1
TOTAL	51

How important is consistency in food quality and service in your decision to return to Wow Momo?
51 responses

Interpretation:

The majority (37 out of 51) consider consistency in food quality and service as either "important" or "very important," emphasizing the significance of maintaining standards.

Findings:

Demographics:

The majority of customers were in the age group of 18-24 (58.82%) and 25-34 (21.57%).

Male customers slightly outnumbered female customers, with 56.86% and 43.14%, respectively.

Education-wise, customers were predominantly Bachelor's (37.25%) and Master's degree holders (45.10%).

Most customers were students (62.75%), followed by employed individuals (23.53%).

Customer Satisfaction:

Visitation frequency varied, with the majority (41.2%) visiting rarely and monthly (31.4%).

The overall satisfaction rating averaged at 2.90, leaning between 'Neutral' and 'Dissatisfied'.

Food quality was the most influential factor for satisfaction (54.90%), followed by menu variety (11.76%).

Customer Loyalty:

While most customers frequently (35.29%) or occasionally (41.18%) recommended Wow Momo, some rarely (17.65%) or never did (5.88%).

The majority (78.43%) had introduced family or friends to Wow Momo.

Feedback provision was somewhat divided, with 50.98% having provided feedback.

Importance of Consistency:

The majority (47.06%) considered consistency in food quality and service 'Important' for them

Conclusion:

The study identifies that Wow Momo's primary customer base comprises predominantly young adults, mainly students, with a preference for affordable, quality fast food. The majority were satisfied with the food quality, although the overall satisfaction rating suggests room for improvement. While there's a consistent trend in recommending and introducing others to Wow Momo, a fair portion doesn't visit frequently. Consistency in food quality and service appears crucial for a considerable segment of the customer base. These findings underscore the need for Wow Momo to focus on enhancing overall customer satisfaction and encouraging frequent visits, considering diverse factors such as varied menu options and improved service efficiency.

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